

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name
Covaci Brindusa

Addresses
71-75 Shelton Street, Covent Garden, London, WC2H9JQ, United Kingdom
200 N Vineyard Blvd Ste A325, Honolulu, HI 96817, USA
+442037699080, +12817544941, +40312295907

Phone
+442037699080, +12817544941, +40312295907

E-mail
cbinternationaluniversity@gmail.com, covacibrindusa@gmail.com

Sex
Feminine

Job wanted/
occupational field
Research, Education

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

- Period
April 2022 – present
- Occupation or position held
President – Rector, Professor, Ph.D. coordinator
- Main activities and responsibilities
University management, Teaching
- Name and address of employer
CBM International University
- Type of business or sector
Education, Research, Management
- Period
July 2020 – present
- Occupation or position held
Senior Researcher
- Main activities and responsibilities
Research and teaching in Economy (Management, Entrepreneurship, Marketing, Accounting, Finance, Commerce, Business and Agri-Business, Informatics) and in Agronomy (Agriculture, Mountain Economy)
- Name and address of employer
Centre for Mountain Economy – Romanian Academy
- Type of business or sector
Research, development, innovation and education
- Period
July 2020 – present
- Occupation or position held
Senior Researcher, Tutor/Instructor & Director
- Main activities and responsibilities
Research and teaching in Economy (Management, Entrepreneurship, Marketing, Accounting, Finance, Commerce, Business and Agri-Business, Informatics) and in Agronomy (Agriculture, Mountain Economy)
- Name and address of employer
Zealandina Agency, United Kingdom
- Type of business or sector
Research, development, innovation and education
- Period
October 2019 – present
- Occupation or position held
Parenting & Preschooler Educator (Homeschooling)
- Main activities and responsibilities
Preschooler - Milestones development (Physical, Cognitive, Linguistic, Social & Emotional), Montessori activities, Structural activities (according to Romanian National Curriculum & Kinedu Company development & learning plans for 2-7 years old)
- Name and address of employer
Kinedu Company, Monterrey Nuevo León – Mexico (New York - USA & Sao Paolo – Brazil, secondary activity points)
- Type of business or sector
E-learning
- Period
October 2015 – Present
- Occupation or position held
Associate Professor, PhD (October 2015), Vice-Rector (April 2016), Senior researcher (November 2017)
- Main activities and responsibilities
Teaching courses and seminars, research
- Name and address of employer
Adventus University, Romania
- Type of business or sector
Didactic, research and management
- Period
August 2014 – June 2020
- Occupation or position held
Senior Researcher
- Main activities and responsibilities
Research and tutoring
- Name and address of employer
Institute for World Economy – Romanian Academy
- Type of business or sector
Research-development- innovation-tutoring
- Period
April 2014 – October 2015
- Occupation or position held
Tutor in social sciences and humanity / start-ups, Teaching project management
- Main activities and responsibilities
Research, innovation and teaching – coordination of a group formed by 24 PhD students and postdoctoral fellows in order to realize their PhD and postdoctoral researches and teaching project management for 255 PhD students and postdoctoral fellows; Project: Horizon 2020 doctoral and postdoctoral studies: promoting the national interest through excellence, competitiveness and responsibility in Romanian fundamental and applied scientific research
- Name and address of employer
Institute for World Economy – Romanian Academy
- Type of business or sector
Research-development- innovation and teaching
- Period
February 2011 – June 2016
- Function or occupied post
President
- Activities and responsibilities
Research-development-innovation-tutoring activities
- Name and address of the employer
Osterreichish-Rumanischer Akademischer Verein, Austria
- Activity type and sector
Research-development-innovation activity
- Period
October 2011 – September 2012
- Function or occupied post
University lecturer, associate, Project manager
- Activities and responsibilities
Didactic activity – Microeconomic, Enterprise economy, Business administration I, Business administration II, Entrepreneurship; Project management activity
- Name and address of the employer
Titu Maiorescu University, Romania
- Activity type and sector
Didactic and management activity
- Period
August 2010 – present
- Function or occupied post
Director, Researcher, Tutor/Instructor
- Activities and responsibilities
Research in economy, 3 research projects
- Name and address of the employer
Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences, Austria & United Kingdom
- Activity type and sector
Coordination and research in economy
- Period
February 2009 – present
- Function or occupied post
Project manager - coordinator (PMC), project member (PM)
- Activities and responsibilities
ESEN - Fundamental programme of the Romanian Academy CFMR (PM), "Practical students - active and integrated students" SHU (PMC), "ProFeminAntrep - Promoting equal opportunities in entrepreneurship" SHU (PMC), "European quality in higher education" SHU (PM), "Doctoral scholarship in order to sustain doctoral research activities in technical

and humanity area, for environment protection and sanity, of national, European and world legislation with eco-economic and socio-economic impact CERDOCT" UNIVNT (PM), "Doctoral scholarship of eco-economic and bio-economic complex learning in order to sustain safety and security food from anthropic ecosystems" (PM) RA-NIER, " New work places in rural area: Romania – Austria and Opportunities for quick integration of unemployed from West and Centre of Romania" (PMC) ORAV, "Juridical studies – between theory and practice" (PMC) AICU-RNI, "Chance to education, your chance!" (PMC) BCM

- Name and address of the employer
Centre for Financial and Monetary Research (CFMR) & National Institute for Economic Research – Romanian Academy (RA-NIER), Spiru Haret University (SHU), Alexandru Ioan Cuza University - Romanian Notarial Institute (AICU-RNI), Nicolae Titulescu University (UNIVNT), Osterreichish-Rumanischer Akademischer Verein (ORAV), Bethlem Church Medgidia (BCM)
Development & research projects
October 2008 – present
Senior Researcher
Research in economy, 2 research projects
- Activity type and sector
• Period
- Function or occupied post
- Activities and responsibilities
- Name and address of the employer
Advancement of Scholarly Research Centre, New York, United States of America
Research in economy
October 2007 – September 2014
Assistant professor/University lecturer, Director Research Centre
Didactic activity – Credit and banking, Monetary and financial economy, Money and monetary policies, Risk economy, Econometric and economic forecasting, Economic efficiency, Statistic, Financial policies and institutions, Financial enterprise management
- Activity type and sector
• Period
- Function or occupied post
- Activities and responsibilities
- Name and address of the employer
Spiru Haret University, Romania
Didactic activity
October 2002 – November 2009
Educational Director, Projects member
Leonardo da Vinci, Comenius - Youth Europe
- Activity type and sector
• Period
- Function or occupied post
- Activities and responsibilities
- Name and address of the employer
Dr. I.C. Cantacuzino College, Romania
External funds projects
October 2000 – August 2007
Professor
Didactic and research for economic and informatics disciplines, Executive Director
Virgil Madgearu Economical College, Industrial Electronics College, Dr. I. C. Cantacuzino College and Ecoprof College
- Activity type and sector
• Period
- Function or occupied post
- Activities and responsibilities
- Name and address of the employer
Industrial Electronic College
External funds projects
October 1997 – September 2007, September 2012 – December 2014
Director for marketing, Consultant marketing / Financial counselling
Consulting in economy, marketing, PR
SC Amway Marketing Romania SRL / SC Dana'S SRL / AIG Life Romania / Raiffeisen Banca pentru Locuinte Consulting
- Activity type and sector

EDUCATION AND TUTORING

- Period
November 2021
Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages / Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TESOL/TEFL) - Graduate certificate
English Teaching, English Pedagogy
- Qualification / diploma
- Disciplines studied / professional competencies
World TESOL Academy, United Kingdom
Continuing education
November 2021
Tutor/Instructor/Trainer - Graduate certificate
Teaching, Instructor, Training, Adult education
- Name and institution type
- Level in national or international classification
- Period
- Qualification / diploma
- Disciplines studied / professional competencies
Teaching & Training Center, Romania
Continuing education
October 2021
Specialized educator Graduate certificate
Teaching, Pedagogy, Children education, Social work support, Caregiving
- Name and institution type
- Level in national or international classification
- Period
- Qualification / diploma
- Disciplines studied / professional competencies
Saint Giovanni Bosco Foundation, Romania
Continuing education
1 October 2020 – present
PhD diploma
Agronomy, Agriculture, Mountain Economy
- Name and institution type
- Level in national or international classification
- Period
- Qualification / diploma
- Disciplines studied / professional competencies
Oradea University, Romania
PhD candidate, Level 6
September 2020
English language certificate, Advanced level
English language
- Name and institution type
- Level in national or international classification
- Period
- Qualification / diploma
- Disciplines studied / professional competencies
Transylvania University of Brasov, Romania
Continuous education
1 March 2013 – 30 May 2014
Postdoctoral diploma
Eco-economy, Bio-economy, Banca electronica, Eco-banking, Bio-banking, Financial and cybernetic security
- Name and institution type
- Level in national or international classification
- Period

disciplines, new studies programmes and modification of the standardization area
- I have abilities in coordination and management, and I am doing volunteering (Pro-Life Foundation, International Children Care, Rise and Walk Association)

FOREIGN LANGUAGES

English (Duolingo 110), Italian (well), French (well)

SOCIAL SKILLS AND ABILITIES

I have competencies in working with a multitude of people, in different areas

ORGANIZATIONAL SKILLS AND ABILITIES

- Organising teams; - Organizing events, workshops, conferences; - Writing and implementing projects: national funds, European and international (CSA USA; Romanian Academy/INCE, ARACIS, UTM, ORAV Austria, Zealandina Ag UK)

COMPUTER SKILLS AND ABILITIES

Utilizer: Windows, Linux, Microsoft Office, Acrobat Reader, Autocad, LabView, HTML, SPSS
Programmer: Pascal, C/C++, Java, FoxPro, SQL

01/29/2022

